

1 **The Dynamics of Megafire Smoke Plumes in Climate**
2 **Models: Why a Converged Solution Matters for**
3 **Physical Interpretations**

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8 **Key Points:**

- 9 • Simulations of megafire smoke plumes require fully resolved dynamics ($\sim 8 \Delta x$)
10 in order to accurately characterize plume properties (e.g., black carbon fraction)
11 • For the 2017 British Columbia event, smoke injected at ~ 12 km height requires
12 a reduction in black carbon fraction by 50% to match observations for external
13 mixtures
14 • Analysis of the vorticity dynamics shows that smoke plume anti-cyclonic vortices
15 form (decay) due to the dilution (concentration) of cyclonic absolute vorticity

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Abstract

As the climate system warms, megafires have become more frequent with devastating effects. A byproduct of these events is the creation of smoke plumes that can rise into the stratosphere and spread across the globe where they reside for many months. To gain a deeper understanding of the plume dynamics, global climate simulations of a megafire were performed at a wide range of grid spacings from 2.0° down to 7 km, including a 7 km nonhydrostatic experiment. The analysis focuses on how the resolved dynamics affects the specification of the plume characteristics such as injection height and black carbon (BC) mass. Prior studies initialize the smoke plume at one or a few grid points and this is shown here to produce severely dissipative dynamics. In order to validate such simulations with observations, enhancements of the plume characteristics to offset the dissipation is necessary. Using a numerically converged simulation, sensitivity tests show that to approximate the observed stratospheric lifetime, a reduction in BC fraction by 50% is necessary for external mixtures. The vorticity dynamics of the plume is also analyzed with a Lagrangian budget to understand the mechanisms responsible for the evolution of a collocated anticyclonic vortex. The results can be distilled down into a simple conceptual model. As the plume rises, the air diverges at the top of the updraft where the largest concentrations of smoke are found. This divergence induces a dilution of the background cyclonic absolute vorticity producing an anticyclonic vortex. Vortex decay occurs from opposite arguments.

Plain Language Summary

Recently, there has been an increase in large and intense wildfires (“megafires”) across the Earth in response to global warming. These megafire events produce large amounts of smoke that can rise high up in the atmosphere to a level well above clouds and weather. The smoke can stay at these high levels for long periods of time and spread across much of the Earth, which blocks sunlight from reaching the surface. It is important to understand the properties of these smoke plumes and how to correctly predict their consequences on human life. However, uncertainties in both observations and models make it difficult to achieve these goals. In particular, models contain various sources of uncertainty that can interact in complex ways. In this paper, we show that previous research has used a model grid spacing that does not sample the plume accurately, which leads to errors that affect the interpretation of the smoke properties, evolution of the plume and potential climatic effects. By choosing a model grid spacing that accurately samples the plume structure, the errors in the dynamics component of the model can be minimized, providing a baseline for reducing uncertainty in other parts of the system.

1 Introduction

In the last several years, there has been a dramatic increase in large, intense wildfires (“megafires”) in various regions of the world that have burned millions of acres of forests, destroyed homes and businesses and resulted in substantial deaths (e.g., Jolly et al., 2015; Wikipedia contributors, 2022). The production of smoke from these fires can be rapidly transported deep into the stratosphere through a combination of pyrocumulonimbus (pyroCb) events and radiation-driven lift, where it can spread globally and reside for many months to years (e.g., Fromm et al., 2005; Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018). Recent megafires in British Columbia (2017; BC17) and Australia (2019/2020) have produced stratospheric aerosol mass burdens between $\sim 0.2 - 1.0$ Tg, which is equivalent to that from a moderate volcanic eruption (Peterson et al., 2021).

A natural question to ask is: what are the impacts of these stratospheric smoke plumes on climate? While some studies have estimated the net radiative forcing resulting from megafires, the global mean of this forcing is usually small and sometimes of opposite sign

(Christian et al., 2019; Das et al., 2021), casting doubt on their effects on the climate system. Christian et al. (2019) studied the BC17 megafire event and estimated a direct, top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA), net radiative forcing between $+0.01$ and $+0.02 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ (global mean over 2 - 3 months) compared to values between -0.7 and -1.3 Wm^{-2} (global mean over 1 - 2 months) from the 2008 Kasatochi volcano eruption (Wang et al., 2013). However, Christian et al. (2019) did not employ a coupled climate model in their radiative forcing calculations, eliminating aerosol indirect effects, which could result in significant uncertainty. Das et al. (2021) performed coupled climate model simulations of the BC17 event and found TOA forcing of $-0.03 \pm 0.01 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ (global mean over 2 - 3 months). While the BC17 forcings are small and potentially within the noise, for larger megafires, such as the 2019/2020 Australian event, the radiative effects can be significant with TOA forcing values of $-0.31 \pm 0.09 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ (global mean over 1 month) (Khaykin et al., 2020) and mean surface temperature cooling of up to -0.2 K (D'Angelo et al., 2022).

It is clear that more in-depth studies are needed to understand the potential regional and global effects of megafire smoke plumes. To provide a more comprehensive analysis of potential climatic effects, it is important to understand the mechanisms controlling the transport of smoke and to quantify characteristics of the smoke plumes such as total mass, breakdown of that mass into organic aerosol (the focus here is on organic carbon or OC) and black carbon (BC) fractions, mean particle radius, peak height and stratospheric residence time, among others. Several recent studies have analyzed specific megafire cases to achieve this understanding and they typically utilize either satellite observations alone or in combination with climate models. The focus of the present paper is on the plume and vorticity dynamics of the BC17 megafire and therefore, a brief description of this event is discussed next. However, the discussion, results and conclusions of the present paper are sufficiently general such that they are relevant to a broader scope of megafire events.

The BC17 megafire was initiated on August 12, 2017 and produced a series of seven discrete pyroCbs with five of them occurring before sunset (lasting for about a 5 h period) and two occurring after sunset (Fromm et al., 2021). Lidar satellite observations indicated that smoke from the pyroCbs reached altitudes of up to $\sim 13 \text{ km}$ about 8 h after the 5 h pulsing period at 1045 UTC 13 August, which is $\sim 1 \text{ km}$ above the local tropopause of $\sim 12 \text{ km}$ (Peterson et al., 2018). The smoke is thought to have been directly injected into the stratosphere by the pyroCbs, but there are uncertainties with this interpretation. About 33 h later at 1930 UTC 14 August, lidar observations clearly show significant smoke at heights of $\sim 13.5 \text{ km}$, illustrating the important role of radiative lofting effects (Torres et al., 2020). The peak height of the smoke plume was $\sim 22 \text{ km}$ about three weeks after the fire initiation with elevated lidar backscatter detected for ~ 4 months or more (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018). In addition, the ascent rate of the BC17 plume in the first few days was estimated at $\sim 2 - 3 \text{ km/day}$ and over a three week time period averaged $\sim 0.5 \text{ km/day}$ (Khaykin et al., 2018).

Initially, the smoke is confined to the cores of the pyroCbs, which have a scale on the order of 10 km . However, as the pyroCbs merge and penetrate the tropopause, their outflow coupled with the strong winds near the tropopause can spread the smoke to a large horizontal area, on the order of many thousands of square kilometers. Peterson et al. (2018) estimated a smoke area of $\sim 800,000 \text{ km}^2$ based on an aerosol index from satellite observations, but the area of dense smoke is much smaller than this value. Estimates of the total smoke mass produced by the BC17 megafire ($0.1 - 0.3 \text{ Tg}$) were calculated using two methods. The first method integrates the particle mass density over the volume of smoke contained in the stratosphere using lidar data, while the second method uses observations of the total burned area, fuel consumption and smoke emissions. While reasonable estimates can be obtained, there is significant uncertainty ($\sim 50\%$) in the mean mass value of 0.2 Tg .

117 The breakdown of smoke emissions from megafires into BC and OC is critical for
 118 plume lofting effects because BC is a strong absorber of radiation across the solar spec-
 119 trum, while OC, which dominates the total smoke mass, is a very weak absorber. The
 120 associated heating of the plume from these radiative effects can loft the smoke high into
 121 the stratosphere (Malone et al., 1985). Unfortunately, there is also significant uncertainty
 122 in the BC fraction in the range of $\sim 2 - 6\%$ as described below. In addition, the micro-
 123 physical aspects of smoke particle evolution are highly uncertain and they are treated
 124 simply in climate models. The microphysical aspects include mixing processes with other
 125 aerosols and phases of water as well as interactions with radiation (optical properties),
 126 which are complex, variable and difficult to measure.

127 Yu et al. (2019) used the Community Earth System Model (CESM) at $1.9^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$
 128 horizontal resolution and 56 vertical levels (~ 1 km resolution near the tropopause) to
 129 determine the BC content and stratospheric residence time of the BC17 smoke plume.
 130 This was done by perturbing the BC fraction over a range of values (1 - 5 %) and com-
 131 paring the peak height of the simulated plume to satellite observations. The plume was
 132 initialized at 12 - 13 km height, seemingly at one grid point near the fire epicenter, with
 133 0.3 Tg of total mass. With this setup, Yu et al. (2019) inferred that a 2 % BC fraction
 134 best matched observations. They estimated a ~ 5 month stratospheric residence time
 135 (e-folding time) from observations and an ~ 8 month e-folding time from the simulations
 136 with 2% BC fraction. The authors determined that in order to match the observed e-
 137 folding time, a photochemical loss of OC must be invoked.

138 Torres et al. (2020) used the NASA Goddard Earth Observing System (GEOS) global
 139 climate model at ~ 55 km ($\sim 0.5^\circ$) horizontal resolution and 72 vertical levels (also \sim
 140 1 km resolution near the tropopause) to study the BC17 event. The authors used a to-
 141 tal smoke mass of 0.3 Tg and assumed a BC fraction of 2.5%. Independent estimates of
 142 the total smoke mass were computed and they found a range of 0.18 - 0.35 Tg, similar
 143 to Peterson et al. (2018). The smoke mass was spread evenly across a $2^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ area in
 144 the horizontal (4 - 5 grid points covering the plume) and injected uniformly between 10
 145 - 12 km altitude, which is just below the tropopause height. The main takeaway from
 146 this study is the significant impact of radiative self-lofting in driving the plume into the
 147 stratosphere to high altitudes (up to 20 - 22 km height) with diabatic heating rates of
 148 20 K/day or more.

149 Das et al. (2021) used the simulation described in Torres et al. (2020) to study ad-
 150 ditional aspects of the BC17 event, including the radiative forcing discussed above. They
 151 found a stratospheric e-folding time of 140 days (4.67 months) from their simulation af-
 152 ter starting the calculation 38 days from the initial injection. An estimate of this time-
 153 scale from a satellite retrieval was similar (5 months) although the decay rate appears
 154 slightly steeper than the model. Both Christian et al. (2019) and Das et al. (2021) do
 155 not need to include a photochemical loss of OC to approach the observed stratospheric
 156 e-folding time, casting doubt on the results presented in Yu et al. (2019).

157 D'Angelo et al. (2022) (hereafter D22) conducted global simulations of the BC17
 158 event from the CESM and GEOS models to understand the sensitivity of plume peak
 159 height and stratospheric residence time to BC fraction (2 - 6 %), injection height (12 -
 160 14 km), total mass (0.1 - 0.3 Tg) and particle radius (200 - 350 nm). The control sim-
 161 ulations used a BC fraction of 2%, stratospheric injection height of ~ 13.5 km and mean
 162 particle radius of 300 - 350 nm. The total injected mass was 0.4 Tg, but only 0.2 Tg was
 163 injected at ~ 13.5 km height with the other 0.2 Tg spread evenly below this altitude.
 164 This setup mirrors that of Christian et al. (2019). The control setup produced a strato-
 165 spheric e-folding time of ~ 5 months for the CESM model and ~ 6 months for the GEOS
 166 model.

167 D22 found the most sensitive parameters (in order from largest to smallest) to be
 168 plume injection height, total mass/BC fraction (together determine BC load) and par-

169 ticle radius. These parameters are not only sensitive in models, but they have signifi-
 170 cant uncertainty from measurements as described above. The particle sizes, however, have
 171 minimal sensitivity for a reasonable measurement range. The plume injection height is
 172 a consequence of the typically very coarse resolution of climate models, which cannot re-
 173 solve the natural life cycle of pyroCbs in any form. As a result, the altitude that con-
 174 vection transports smoke into the upper atmosphere must be specified to initialize the
 175 model. For the BC17 case, measurements of this altitude are uncertain with values rang-
 176 ing from $\sim 11 - 14$ km.

177 There is another source of uncertainty that has not been addressed methodically
 178 with megafire studies: the effects of resolved energetics in the climate models and feed-
 179 backs to the uncertainties associated with the plume characteristics. Most of the mod-
 180 eling studies are conducted with very coarse grid spacing (e.g., $1^\circ - 2^\circ$) with the plume
 181 initialized at one grid point, although Torres et al. (2020) and Das et al. (2021) used 0.5°
 182 covering the plume with 4 - 5 grid points. What are the effects of higher resolution on
 183 the smoke plume dynamics (e.g., transport, large-scale mixing and interactions with clouds)
 184 and interplay with the specified plume characteristics (e.g., injection height, total smoke
 185 mass and BC fraction)? The purpose of this paper is to answer these questions and make
 186 recommendations to the community for a minimally resolvable modeling system that can
 187 narrow the uncertainty gap for the megafire problem.

188 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, a description of
 189 the numerical model and setup of the simulations is presented. Simulations are conducted
 190 at a wide range of resolutions to study the effects of resolved dynamics: 2.0° , 1.0° , 0.25° ,
 191 7 km and 7 km-nonhydrostatic. Analysis of the characteristics and transport of the sim-
 192 ulated smoke plumes is described in Section 3, which also presents an analysis of the ki-
 193 netic energy spectra of the simulations and discusses the effective resolution of the GEOS
 194 modeling system. Section 4 presents an analysis of the vorticity dynamics of the plumes
 195 and how this relates to the plume lifetime. Important implications of this work for the
 196 megafire problem are given in Section 5. Future work is also discussed in this section.

197 **2 Numerical Simulations**

198 **2.1 Description and setup of climate model**

199 To examine the global effects of localized megafire smoke plumes, numerical sim-
 200 ulations of the BC17 event were conducted with the atmospheric component of the NASA
 201 GEOS climate model. The NASA GEOS is a finite volume general circulation model that
 202 solves the hydrostatic or nonhydrostatic equations of motion on a cubed sphere grid with
 203 a Lagrangian vertical coordinate (Lin, 2004). The dynamic core is coupled to various phys-
 204 ical models for moist processes, radiation, turbulence, gravity wave drag, etc. (Molod
 205 et al., 2015) and is initialized with reanalysis data that incorporates various observations
 206 (MERRA-2) (Rienecker et al., 2008). In this study, the Goddard Chemistry, Aerosol, Ra-
 207 diation and Transport (GOCART) (Chin et al., 2002) model is utilized to represent smoke
 208 plumes with a focus on the bins for BC and OC aerosol. The aerosols in GOCART are
 209 treated as an external mixture and are fully coupled to the dynamic core and radiation
 210 packages. The BC and OC complex refractive indices, where the imaginary part is re-
 211 sponsible for absorption of radiation, are set to $1.75-0.45i$ and $1.53-0.005i$, respectively.
 212 The source of BC/OC for the BC17 event is described below and the sinks include wet
 213 scavenging and dry deposition. Given the focus on the stratosphere, the dry deposition
 214 processes are most important. This dry deposition is a parameterization of gravitational
 215 settling based on particle size and air viscosity (Chin et al., 2002). Also note that no in-
 216 teractive chemistry model is employed in the simulations. These simplifications reduce
 217 the degrees of freedom in the simulations and places the focus of the analysis on the dy-
 218 namics of the problem.

219 Simulations with GEOS are conducted with a wide range of uniform horizontal grid
 220 spacings across the globe: 2.0°, 1.0°, 0.25° and 7 km. The vertical grid for all simulations
 221 was set to 72 hybrid sigma-pressure vertical layers from the surface to the model top at
 222 0.01 hPa. Utilization of the same vertical grid for all simulations enables a direct com-
 223 parison of the resolved energetics of each simulation. The vertical grid spacing is ~ 1 km
 224 where the smoke plume is initialized in the stratosphere. These simulations are all run
 225 with hydrostatic dynamics, but an additional run at 7 km is conducted with nonhydro-
 226 static dynamics to examine the effects of the vertical inertial terms (advection of ver-
 227 tical velocity plus the local time tendency), as well as a diffusion term, on the plume heights
 228 and stratospheric residence time of the smoke. In general, nonhydrostatic effects become
 229 more important for scales of ~ 10 km and below (e.g., Weisman et al., 1997). Also, note
 230 that the GEOS model is run in a “free” mode without observational nudging and in this
 231 sense represents a true predictive simulation. The MERRA-2 reanalysis fields are used
 232 as initial conditions for the simulations and the model is started at 2100 UTC 9 August
 233 2017, which is about three days prior to the injection of smoke. This allows the model
 234 to spin-up for a period of time and develop a more robust energy spectrum.

235 The BC17 plume is represented in the model by injecting smoke mass following the
 236 specification outlined in Christian et al. (2019) and D22 due to the simplicity and abil-
 237 ity to compare with prior work. For the 2.0° simulation, the smoke mass is initialized
 238 at a single grid point (close to 53.5°N, 123.0°W; an approximate epicenter for the BC17
 239 plume) with 0.2 Tg injected at ~ 13.5 km height in the stratosphere and 0.2 Tg spread
 240 evenly in the troposphere. Of the total mass, 98% is specified as OC and 2% as BC fol-
 241 lowing the results of Yu et al. (2019) and D22. This smoke profile is held fixed in the model
 242 for a 5 h time period starting at 1900 UTC 12 August 2017. A mean particle radius of
 243 350 nm is used for all simulations and is held fixed. This particle radius is motivated by
 244 observations of thick coatings in upper tropospheric smokes plumes (Ditas et al., 2018;
 245 Katich & coauthors, 2023). Similarities and differences of the smoke plume initialization
 246 described here with that from prior work can be found in the introduction section.

247 The setup of the simulations at the other grid spacings is identical to that described
 248 above except the smoke mass is spread evenly across the higher resolution grids to match
 249 the 2.0° grid cell area. For example, the smoke mass is spread evenly across 4 grid points
 250 or grid cells (2 in each horizontal dimension) for the 1.0° simulation, 64 grid points (8
 251 in each horizontal dimension) for the 0.25° and 1024 grid points (32 in each horizontal
 252 dimension) for the 7 km runs in the same location as the 2.0° cell. Integration of the to-
 253 tal smoke mass on the native cubed sphere grid showed nearly identical values across all
 254 simulations indicating a consistent set of initial forcing with uniform smoke concentra-
 255 tion. For post-processing, all model output is interpolated to a regularly spaced latitude/longitude
 256 grid that matches the listed simulation resolution.

257 Lastly, to evaluate the dynamical accuracy of the simulations, the 7 km hydrostatic
 258 experiment is used as the high resolution reference to compare the other grid spacing runs
 259 (see Section 3.1 and 3.2). This is done to establish relative truth among the various sim-
 260 ulations and find an optimal resolution for further sensitivity tests, which are compared
 261 to observations in Section 3.3.

262 **3 Characteristics of Plume Evolution**

263 **3.1 Stratospheric Lifetime and Smoke Structure**

264 To summarize the smoke plume evolution in the simulations, a time series of the
 265 globally integrated stratospheric smoke burden at a wide range of horizontal grid spac-
 266 ings is presented in Fig. 1. In this analysis, the stratosphere is loosely defined as heights
 267 above 150 hPa or ~ 12.5 km in the region where the plume is present. All simulations
 268 are run up until the plume stratospheric lifetime, which is defined as where the peak strato-

269 spheric mass (sampled at ~ 6 days into the simulations) falls off to $1/e$, using the glob-
 270 ally integrated values shown in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1 and all other figures shown in this pa-
 271 per, time refers to the number of days after the start of the plume forcing (1900 UTC
 272 12 August 2017).

Figure 1: Time series of the globally integrated stratospheric (above 150 hPa) smoke burden in Tg for simulations at a wide range of horizontal grid spacings. The first output time is 6.2 days into the simulations. The lifetimes in months are 3.5, 5.9, 7.2, 6.9, 6.8 for the 2.0°, 1.0°, 0.25°, 7 km and 7km nonhydrostatic simulations, respectively.

273 Figure 1 shows that the 2.0° simulation falls off very rapidly with a lifetime of 3.5
 274 months, followed by the 1.0° simulation at 5.9 months, 7 km nonhydrostatic at 6.8 months,
 275 7 km at 6.9 months and 0.25° at 7.2 months. Using the 7 km simulation as the high res-
 276 olution reference to evaluate the other hydrostatic runs, the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations sig-
 277 nificantly underestimate the stratospheric lifetime by $\sim 50\%$ and 15% , respectively, while
 278 the 0.25° simulation only slightly overestimates the lifetime by $\sim 4\%$. The 7 km nonhy-
 279 drostatic lifetime is slightly less than the corresponding 7 km hydrostatic value, which
 280 indicates that nonhydrostatic dynamics (including the vertical inertial term as well as
 281 a diffusion term) are contributing an overall dissipative effect on the plume lofting and
 282 stratospheric lifetime. Even finer grid spacing than 7 km will likely lead to additional
 283 small differences, but such simulations are an enormous computational burden and are
 284 left for future work.

285 Figure 1 also shows there is some variability in the individual curves, with the ex-
 286 ception of the 2.0° simulation, at time periods less than about 30 - 50 days due to vari-
 287 ability in the horizontal and vertical transport of the smoke. After about 50 days, the

288 curves become smooth, which is consistent with the slow and steady removal of smoke
 289 from the stratosphere by sedimentation. It is difficult to estimate the stratospheric life-
 290 time from observations due to smoke plume detection issues (limited sampling in space
 291 and time, signal-to-noise ratio of instrument, etc), but studies have indicated that ~ 5
 292 months is a reasonable value (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2019;
 293 Das et al., 2021). However, in this section, we are not as concerned with the absolute
 294 truth of the simulations, which are only quasi-realistic representations of the BC17 event.
 295 For example, there are various unknown and uncertain factors surrounding the plume
 296 characteristics as described in the introduction. Instead, we are focused on studying the
 297 relative truth of the simulations and the reasons for the wide range of variability pre-
 298 sented in Fig. 1 that can guide more focused case studies of the BC17 event or other megafire
 299 cases.

Figure 2: Zonal mean total smoke mixing ratio in kg/kg at 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) into the simulations for varying resolutions, (a) 2.0° (b) 1.0° (c) 0.25° and (d) 7 km. The red line shows the tropopause height.

300 The stratospheric lifetime discussed above is directly related to the peak height the
 301 plume reaches in each simulation. Figure 2 shows the zonal mean smoke mixing ratio
 302 as a function of latitude and height at 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) into the simu-
 303 lations. The peak height of the plume, defined qualitatively as the leading edge of the
 304 large smoke mixing ratio core, varies widely with resolution. The peak height values are
 305 ~ 18 km, 23 km, 32 km and 30 km in the 2.0° , 1.0° , 0.25° and 7 km simulations, respec-
 306 tively. Relative to the 7 km reference simulation, the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations drasti-

307 cally underestimate the peak height by 40% and 23%, respectively, while the 0.25°
 308 simulation slightly overestimates the peak height by about 6%. The 2.0° and 1.0° simu-
 309 lations have one primary smoke core that is concentrated near 60° latitude, while the 0.25°
 310 and 7 km simulations have two cores with one near 60° latitude and the other closer to
 311 70° latitude. The two smoke cores are more distinct in the 7 km simulation. The vast
 312 majority of the smoke is above the tropopause at this time in all simulations, but the
 313 dense smoke is closer to this boundary in the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations.

Figure 3: The same as in Fig. 2, only at 16.2 days (0000 UTC 29 August).

314 At 16.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) into the simulations, shown in Fig. 3, the peak
 315 height of the plumes are ~ 19 km, 30 km, 38 km and 35 km in the 2.0°, 1.0°, 0.25° and
 316 7 km simulations, respectively. The 2.0° and 1.0° simulations underestimate the peak height
 317 by ~ 46% and 14%, respectively, while the 0.25° simulation slightly overestimates this
 318 height by ~ 8%. The rise rate of the 1.0° simulation is largest at 0.7 km/day, followed
 319 by the 0.25° (0.6 km/day), 7 km (0.5 km/day) and 2.0° (0.1 km/day). Most of the plumes
 320 are concentrated into one column with the exception of the 7 km run, which continues
 321 to display two main cores with one centered at ~ 45° latitude and 23 km height and the
 322 other at ~ 80° latitude and 26 km height. Nearly all the smoke is above the tropopause
 323 at this time period, but the 2.0° simulation (Fig. 3a) shows large concentrations sitting
 324 very close to the edge of the boundary. Note that the peak height of the plumes over time
 325 are found at ~ 20 - 25 days into the simulations with values not much larger than that
 326 described here at 16.2 days.

327 The vertical transport of the plumes observed in Figs. 2 and 3 is due to the self-
 328 lofting effect described in the introduction whereby BC absorbs solar radiation and forms
 329 a heating anomaly, which causes a buoyant updraft. The large variability in the solu-
 330 tions with grid spacing, which all have the same plume initialization and model setup,
 331 is due to the effects of resolved energetics in the model. Detailed examination of this ef-
 332 fect will be presented in Section 3.2.

Figure 4: Vertically integrated total smoke mixing ratio in kg/Tg over the entire model atmosphere at 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) into the simulations for varying resolutions, (a) 2.0° (b) 1.0° (c) 0.25° and (d) 7 km.

333 Figure 4 shows the horizontal structure of the smoke plume at 6.2 days (0000 UTC
 334 19 August) by vertically integrating the total smoke mixing ratio over the entire model
 335 atmosphere. At this time period, the 2.0° run (Fig. 4a) shows a single ball of smoke lo-
 336 cated over the Hudson Bay in Canada with a long tail of elevated concentrations extend-
 337 ing across the Atlantic Ocean and into Western Europe. The other resolution simula-
 338 tions have similar placement of the large-scale features, but the single ball of smoke in
 339 the 2.0° run is broken down into increasingly smaller-scale structures that move smoke
 340 further outward from the core region. For example, in the 1.0° (Fig. 4b), 0.25° (Fig. 4c)
 341 and 7 km (Fig. 4d) simulations, high concentrations of smoke are found in the South-
 342 eastern United States and in the 0.25° and 7 km runs more smoke has moved North and
 343 West into far Northern Canada near the Beaufort Sea. The main location of the smoke
 344 plume over Northeastern Canada (near Hudson Bay) depicted in the modeling results
 345 are in general agreement with satellite observations close to this time period (\sim 19 Au-
 346 gust, 2017) (Khaykin et al., 2018).

347 At 16.2 days (0000 UTC 29 August) (Fig. 5), the horizontal structure of the smoke
 348 plume is significantly different between the various resolution simulations. In the 2.0°
 349 run (Fig. 5a) the highest smoke concentrations are no longer organized into a coherent,
 350 circular structure but instead are stretched and diffused over the Greenland region. The
 351 other resolution simulations display a concentrated, circular structure with peak smoke
 352 mixing ratio values at the center. In the 1.0° run (Fig. 5b) this structure is located over
 353 Eastern Canada while in the 0.25° run (Fig. 5c) the ball of smoke is centered just off of
 354 Greenland. In the 7 km run (Fig. 5d), two circular regions of smoke exist with the larger
 355 feature located over the Northern Great Plains of the United States and the smaller fea-

Figure 5: The same as in Fig. 4, only at 16.2 days (0000 UTC 29 August).

356 ture located just to the West of Greenland. Lower values of smoke mixing ratio are scat-
 357 tered North of 30° N latitude in roughly similar locations in all simulations.

358 Satellite observations close to this time period (\sim 29 August, 2017) (Khaykin et
 359 al., 2018) indicate that the smoke plume has encircled the globe and is located back near
 360 Western Canada, which is in closer agreement with the 7 km resolution simulation. How-
 361 ever, at this stage of the paper, we are only establishing relative truth between the simu-
 362 lations and their variability, with the 7 km hydrostatic run serving as the high resolu-
 363 tion reference. The horizontal structure differences between the various resolution simu-
 364 lations at this time is due to the differing altitudes of the plumes and associated wind
 365 fields that drive the transport at those altitudes as well as the nonlinear evolution. The
 366 nonlinear evolution is dependent on the resolved energetics of each simulation and will
 367 cause greater divergence among the simulation members as time moves forward. This
 368 is partly why the smoke horizontal structure at 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) is in much
 369 better agreement than that shown at 16.2 days (0000 UTC 29 August).

370 3.2 Kinetic Energy Spectra

371 The previous section demonstrated large variability in the stratospheric lifetime
 372 and smoke structure as a function of model grid spacing for the exact same parameters
 373 defining the initialized smoke plume. The main source of this variability is the resolved
 374 energetics of the GEOS modeling system and the associated sampling of the initialized
 375 smoke plume. To demonstrate this point, spectral analysis of the model data is performed
 376 using Fourier transforms, which decompose a signal into the fundamental modes of vari-
 377 ability. This information can be used to study where energy resides in a numerical model
 378 and how it evolves in time across various length scales.

379 The discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of a variable Ψ in one spatial dimension λ
 380 (representing longitude in this study) on a periodic domain with constant grid spacing
 381 can be written

$$382 \quad \Psi(\lambda_n) = \sum_{m=-Q}^Q F(k_m) e^{ik_m \lambda_n} = F(0) + 2 \left| \sum_{m=1}^Q F(k_m) e^{ik_m \lambda_n} \right| \quad (1)$$

383 where $\lambda_n = L(n-1)/N$ is the position along the λ dimension for index n over domain
 384 length L with N grid points, $k_m = 2\pi m/L$ is the wavenumber for index m , and Q rep-
 385 represents the highest wavenumber index on the grid (length scale of two times the grid spac-
 386 ing). The complex Fourier coefficients are given by

$$387 \quad F(k_m) = N^{-1} \sum_{n=1}^N \Psi(\lambda_n) e^{-ik_m \lambda_n}. \quad (2)$$

388 In the calculation of the DFT, it is common practice to report on the positive wavenum-
 389 bers only, which requires multiplying wavenumbers larger than zero by a factor of two
 390 to account for the removal of the negative side of the spectrum. For each model simu-
 391 lation, the DFT is computed for each horizontal velocity component along the λ direc-
 392 tion according to the equations above and the horizontal kinetic energy spectrum per
 393 unit mass as a function of wavenumber or wavelength is calculated,

$$394 \quad E(k) = \frac{\hat{u}^2 + \hat{v}^2}{2} \quad (3)$$

Figure 6: Horizontal kinetic energy spectra (m^2/s^2) averaged over the $40^\circ - 70^\circ N$ latitude band and $150 - 10 hPa$ in height at various resolutions in GEOS for (a) 1.2 days (0000 UTC 14 August), (b) 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August), (c) 11.2 days (0000 UTC 24 August) and (d) 16.2 days (0000 UTC 29 August) into the simulations. The dashed black and purple lines denote the -3 and $-5/3$ spectral slopes of large-scale and mesoscale kinetic energy, respectively, from theory and observations. The “P” letter marks the scale of the initial smoke plume forcing.

395 where the hat over the velocity variables denotes the DFT field. The kinetic energy spec-
 396 trum is then averaged over the 40°N - 70°N latitudinal band and the 150 - 10 hPa layer
 397 where the smoke plume activity is largest.

398 Figure 6 shows the mean horizontal kinetic energy spectra for the various resolu-
 399 tion simulations at early time periods ($t \leq \sim 16$ days) in the simulations when much of
 400 the lofting dynamics takes place. The vertical transport of the plume is tied into the hor-
 401 izontal divergence, which is proportional to the horizontal kinetic energy, through the
 402 mass continuity equation. In the hydrostatic constraint used by most of the simulations
 403 shown in this paper, the vertical transport is directly connected with the horizontal di-
 404 vergence. Thus, regions of weak horizontal kinetic energy tend to have weak horizontal
 405 divergence and associated vertical transport. Strong vertical transport arises from op-
 406 posite arguments. At all time periods shown in Fig. 6, the kinetic energy is significantly
 407 damped in the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations (especially the 2.0° run) relative to the 0.25° and
 408 7 km simulations from scales of ~ 200 km - 1000 km. Most of the plume dynamics are
 409 occurring within this wavelength band given that the scale of the initial disturbance is
 410 ~ 450 km (marked in Fig. 6), which is near the minimum resolvable wavelength of the
 411 2.0° simulation ($2 \Delta x$, where Δx is the length of a grid cell in the horizontal dimension).
 412 The 0.25° simulation spectra are very similar to the 7 km simulation spectra in the \sim
 413 200 km - 1000 km wavelength band, which indicates that the 0.25° simulation is nearly
 414 converged for the majority of the plume dynamics. This result is consistent with the statis-
 415 tics presented in Section 3.1, where the 0.25° run produced small errors relative to the
 416 7 km reference simulation. Furthermore, Fig. 6 illustrates that only the 0.25° and 7 km
 417 simulations match the slopes of kinetic energy from theory and observations (e.g., Nas-
 418 trom & Gage, 1985). In the ~ 200 km - 1000 km wavelength band, the 0.25° and 7 km
 419 simulations tend to follow a -3 spectral slope (“large scales”) at 1.2 (0000 UTC 14 Au-
 420 gust) and 6.2 (0000 UTC 19 August) days (Figs. 6a and b, respectively), but evolve a
 421 bit closer to a -5/3 slope (“mesoscales”) at 11.2 (0000 UTC 24 August) and 16.2 (0000
 422 UTC 29 August) days (Figs. 6c and d, respectively). This shift is subtle and not overly
 423 significant given that there is an overlap in the observed spectral slopes in this wavelength
 424 band.

425 Figure 6 also shows the 0.25° simulation has damped kinetic energy relative to the
 426 7 km run from scales of ~ 50 km - 300 km, including some subtle temporal variability
 427 in the spectra. The wavelength where the 0.25° run begins to dissipate kinetic energy
 428 relative to the 7 km run narrows from ~ 300 km wavelength (Figs. 6a,b,c) down to \sim
 429 200 km wavelength (Fig. 6d). These results indicate that the effective resolution of the
 430 GEOS modeling system is $\sim 7 - 8 \Delta x$, which is similar to other global modeling systems
 431 (e.g., Skamarock et al., 2014). *Thus, in order to produce a dynamically accurate and well-*
 432 *resolved simulation, the smoke plume must be sampled by the model grid with ~ 8 grid*
 433 *cells, which should produce the correct slope of kinetic energy as demonstrated in Fig. 6.*

434 3.3 Optimal Simulations

435 Given that the 0.25° spacing simulation produced a dynamically accurate solution,
 436 how should the other uncertain parameters defining the smoke plume (injection height,
 437 total smoke mass, BC fraction and particle radius) be specified to produce an optimal
 438 simulation?

439 Several sensitivity tests were conducted with 0.25° spacing to examine the optimal
 440 settings of these parameters relative to observations. The observations used to constrain
 441 this exercise are estimates of the stratospheric lifetime of the smoke plume (~ 5 months)
 442 (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2019; Das et al., 2021) and to some
 443 extent peak heights (~ 22 km) (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018; Das et al.,
 444 2021).

Table 1: Smoke plume and resolution settings for different model experiments. Note that the mass column refers to the injected stratospheric mass only. The “N” in “7kmN” refers to nonhydrostatic dynamics while all other grid spacings are run with hydrostatic.

Experiment	Injection Height	Mass	BC Fraction	Model Grid Spacing
Control	13.5 km	0.2 Tg	2%	2.0°/1.0°/0.25°/7km/7kmN
Perturb1	11.5 km	0.2 Tg	2%	0.25°
Perturb2	12.5 km	0.2 Tg	2%	0.25°
Perturb3	12.5 km	0.2 Tg	0.5%/0.75%	0.25°

445 The injection height used in the initial simulations (13.5 km) was determined to
 446 be too high based on observational estimates that placed the plumes at 11.5 - 12.5 km
 447 height with the best estimate likely at or slightly above the local tropopause height (\sim
 448 12 km) (Peterson et al., 2018). This injection height is also utilized in previous model-
 449 ing studies (e.g., Yu et al., 2019). For the sensitivity tests discussed here, simulations
 450 were performed with an injection height of 11.5 km and 12.5 km, given the vertical grid
 451 spacing of the chosen model grid (1.0 km). The total column smoke mass (0.4 Tg with
 452 0.2 Tg injected in the stratosphere) and particle radius (350 nm) were not changed. Some
 453 short (60 day) sensitivity tests that examined the impact of the 0.2 Tg of smoke spread
 454 evenly throughout the troposphere were also conducted. These tests showed that by re-
 455 moving the 0.2 Tg of smoke in the troposphere, the total smoke mass in the stratosphere
 456 is reduced by only $\sim 4\%$. This indicates that for the distribution of mass utilized here,
 457 the amount of smoke rising into the stratosphere from the troposphere is quite small. Thus,
 458 our focus is on the smoke injected in the stratosphere. For the 11.5 km injection height
 459 a BC mass fraction of 2% was utilized, as in the initial set of simulations, while for the
 460 12.5 km height, BC mass fractions of 0.5%, 0.75% and 2% were performed. Table 1 sum-
 461 marizes the smoke plume and model resolution settings utilized for these sensitivity tests
 462 along with those for the control experiments.

463 Figure 7 shows the results of some of these 0.25° sensitivity tests in terms of the
 464 horizontally averaged total smoke mixing ratio. The center of mass of the smoke plume
 465 is drawn on each simulation as a measure of the plume height. It should be noted that
 466 there are uncertainties comparing this height to observations, such as from lidar, due to
 467 the difficulties in simulating the penetration depth of the instrument signal into the smoke
 468 as well as other instrument effects. Nevertheless, the height metric from the simulations
 469 assists in tuning the simulations to observations.

470 Figure 7a shows results for an injection height of 11.5 km with 2.0% BC fraction,
 471 which produced a 4.4 month e-decay timescale, a bit too short relative to observations.
 472 It appears the height of the plume is too low with peak heights of around 18 km alti-
 473 tude. Figure 7b depicts the smoke evolution for an injection height of 12.5 km with 2.0%
 474 BC fraction. It is clear that the peak heights for this experiment are too high with val-
 475 ues up to nearly 30 km altitude that stay elevated above 20 km altitude for several months.
 476 The e-decay timescale produced from this experiment is 6.3 months, which is too long
 477 relative to observations. Finally, Fig. 7c shows results for an injection height of 12.5 km
 478 only with 0.75% BC fraction. The plume height is more similar to observations than the
 479 other two sensitivity tests with values near 22 - 25 km altitude initially and then a steady
 480 value of ~ 18 km that lasts several months. The e-decay timescale for this experiment
 481 is 5.1 months, which is also very similar to observations.

482 Given that the best estimate for the observed injection height is ~ 12 km and the
 483 model vertical resolution is only ~ 1 km near the tropopause, we assess that the opti-

Figure 7: Horizontally averaged total smoke mixing ratio (kg/Tg) as a function of time and height for 0.25° grid spacing simulations with (a) 11.5 km injection height and 2.0% BC fraction, denoted "Perturb1" in Table 1, (b) 12.5 km injection height and 2.0% BC fraction, denoted "Perturb2" in Table 1 and (c) 12.5 km injection height and 0.75% BC fraction, one of the tests labeled "Perturb3" in Table 1. The black line in each figure denotes the center of mass of the smoke plume.

484 mal BC fraction is $\sim 1\%$. This assessment is based on the simulation with a 12.5 km injection height and 0.75% BC fraction, which best matched observations. The optimal
 485 injection height and 0.75% BC fraction is a 50% reduction from the control experiment as well as prior
 486 studies (e.g., Yu et al., 2019) and requires a numerically converged solution of $\sim 0.25^\circ$
 487 grid spacing. The final optimal smoke plume characteristics for the BC17 event deter-
 488 mined from GEOS simulations are as follows: 0.2 Tg stratospheric smoke mass, 1% BC
 489 mass fraction, 300 - 350 nm particle radius and ~ 12 km injection height. Table 2 lists
 490 the model resolution and optimal smoke plume characteristics determined from various
 491 studies of the BC17 event. The optical properties of the particles, specifically the com-
 492 plex refractive indices, are also listed, which affect the magnitude of the radiative heat-
 493 ing anomaly and associated lofting. Most of the studies use the same or very similar re-
 494 fractive indices with the exception of Yu et al. (2019). This table serves as a quick re-
 495 ference for comparing the essential components of these studies and where the current
 496 study fits into the literature.
 497

498 Recently, aircraft observations of the BC17 plume have been reported in Katich
 499 and coauthors (2023), focused on thickly coated BC. They report BC fractions of 2.8%
 500 +/- 48% (10/1/2017 over a 767 s interception) and 1.24% +/- 48% (10/25/2017 over 2832
 501 s interception). These flight segments imply an average of 1.57% +/- 48% BC fraction
 502 in the sampled one month old smoke (Katich & coauthors, 2023). It is important to note
 503 that the smoke plumes are heterogeneous and the aircraft only samples a limited region
 504 of these plumes. As a result, this mean BC fraction only represents a small portion of
 505 the actual smoke plume. When comparing these observations to numerical models, one
 506 must be cognizant of the larger area represented by the model, which may not be filled
 507 entirely with smoke. Thus, the estimates of BC fraction presented in this study ($\sim 1\%$)
 508 are consistent with the observational sampling described above and the representation
 509 of that sampling in the model.

510 Lastly, all the simulations in this paper utilize externally mixed BC and observa-
 511 tions suggest they are internally mixed (e.g., coated by OC). Coated particles have a spe-
 512 cific light absorption mass cross section about two times larger than uncoated particles.
 513 Thus, internal mixing would need an even lower BC mass fraction in the optimal sim-
 514 ulation to match the observed stratospheric lifetime and peak height (Lee et al., 2022).

Table 2: Model resolution and optimal settings for smoke plume characteristics for BC17 simulations determined from various papers. “Y19” is Yu et al. (2019), “C19” is Christian et al. (2019), “T20” is Torres et al. (2020), “D21” is Das et al. (2021), “D22” is D’Angelo et al. (2022) and “G23” is the current study. The mass column refers to the smoke mass placed at the injection height. All studies use a coupled model (between aerosols, radiation and dynamics) except that of “C19”. The optics column lists the complex refractive indices of BC/OC for each study (NA means not applicable) with T20/D21 using BrC instead of OC. The Y19 and D22 studies use an internal mixing state, while all other studies utilize an external mixing state.

Study	Grid Spacing	Injection Height	BC	Mass	Optics
Y19	1.9° x 2.5°	12 - 13 km	2%	0.3 Tg	1.95-0.79 <i>i</i> /1.4-0.0 <i>i</i>
C19	2.0° x 2.5°	13.7 km	6%	0.2 Tg	NA
T20/D21	0.5°	10 - 12 km	2.5%	0.3 Tg	1.75-0.45 <i>i</i> /1.47-0.016 <i>i</i>
D22	1.0°/1.9° x 2.5°	13.5 km	2%	0.2 Tg	1.7-0.5 <i>i</i> /1.5-0.01 <i>i</i>
G23	0.25°	12 km	1%	0.2 Tg	1.75-0.45 <i>i</i> /1.53-0.005 <i>i</i>

515 4 Vorticity Dynamics

516 4.1 Vortex Structure

517 Previous studies have documented the occurrence of long-lived, anti-cyclonic vor-
 518 tices associated with wildfire smoke plumes as they rise into the stratosphere and travel
 519 across the globe (Khaykin et al., 2020; Kablick et al., 2020; Allen et al., 2020; Lestre-
 520 lin et al., 2021). The collocation of smoke plumes with a vorticity anomaly can enhance
 521 the concentration of smoke, which can lead to greater radiative absorption, self-lofting
 522 and longer stratospheric residence times. In this Section 4.1, the structure of the vor-
 523 ticity anomalies associated with the smoke plumes are presented. In Section 4.2, the vor-
 524 ticity dynamics of the smoke plumes in the GEOS simulations are analyzed to under-
 525 stand how these anomalies are initially formed, maintained and dissipated.

526 While previous studies have relied on potential vorticity (PV) to study these fea-
 527 tures, we focus on the vorticity field for a couple of reasons. First, one of the primary

528 motivations for analyzing PV is to track flow features through the PV conservation prin-
 529 ciple, which is only valid for frictionless, adiabatic motions. The smoke plumes, however,
 530 do not satisfy adiabatic motions due to significant radiative effects, especially during the
 531 early stages of the plume evolution. Thus, the conservation principle does not apply and
 532 other fields, such as the total smoke mixing ratio can be used to track the plumes. Sec-
 533 ond, the PV field does provide a more concise framework for interpreting the interplay
 534 between the dynamics and heating, which is useful. However, our goal here is to under-
 535 stand how the plume vortices are formed and maintained from fundamental variables and
 536 processes predicted or diagnosed from the numerical model, such as velocities and di-
 537 abatic heating. The vorticity equation contains specific terms that allow for this type
 538 of attribution. The relative vorticity evolution equation in isobaric coordinates can be
 539 expressed as

$$540 \quad \frac{D\zeta_p}{Dt} = -(\zeta_p + f) \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{2\Omega \cos\phi}{a} v + \left(\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \frac{\partial u}{\partial p} - \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \frac{\partial v}{\partial p} \right) + \mathbf{D}, \quad (4)$$

542 where ζ_p is the relative vertical vorticity on a surface of constant pressure, f is the Cori-
 543 olis parameter, Ω is the angular frequency of the Earth, ϕ is the latitude, a is the radius
 544 of the Earth and ω is the vertical velocity in pressure coordinates ($\omega = Dp/Dt$). Fol-
 545 lowing a parcel (denoted by the “material tendency” term, $\frac{D\zeta_p}{Dt}$), the evolution of rel-
 546 ative vorticity is controlled by the divergence of pre-existing absolute vorticity (“diver-
 547 gence” term, first term on the right-hand-side (RHS) of Eq. 4), the meridional change
 548 in Earth’s rotation (“beta” term, second term on the RHS) and the tilting of horizon-
 549 tal components of vorticity into the vertical by variations in the vertical velocity (“tilt-
 550 ing” term, third term on the RHS). Finally, the \mathbf{D} term represents sub-grid scale dis-
 551 sipation effects present in the model, which we assume to be small at the vertical lev-
 552 els analyzed here. This term is still useful to include in Eq. 4 for discussion purposes.

553 Figure 8 shows vertically averaged, horizontal cross sections of relative vorticity within
 554 the smoke plumes at 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) into the simulations with various
 555 grid spacings. Vorticity in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-9} kg/kg
 556 (or 1.0 kg/Tg) is averaged above 150 hPa to produce these plots. Each panel in Fig. 8
 557 is approximately centered on the peak value of the total smoke mixing ratio to highlight
 558 the center of mass of the plumes. An anti-cyclonic vortex is present in the core of the
 559 plumes for each simulation as shown by the concentrated regions of negative vorticity.
 560 The peak values are around $-3.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations $\sim -7.5 \times 10^{-5}$
 561 s^{-1} in the 0.25° simulation and $\sim -5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the 7 km simulation. The vortex is
 562 significantly more diffuse and spread out in the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations as compared
 563 to the 0.25° and 7 km runs despite the fact that all simulations start with the same areal
 564 coverage of smoke. Figures 8c and 8d show that more positive vorticity begins to form
 565 and becomes entrained into the primary anti-cyclonic vortex in the higher resolution sim-
 566 ulations. This is tied into the horizontal convergence and associated vertical transport,
 567 which is well resolved in the 0.25° and 7 km simulations as described in Section 3.2.

568 The zonal mean, vertical structure of the vorticity anomalies is shown in Fig. 9 at
 569 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) into the simulations. Similar to the horizontal cross sec-
 570 tions in Fig. 8, the 1.0° and 2.0° simulations are progressively more diffuse than the other
 571 resolutions. The circulation depths are also shallower in the coarse resolution simulations
 572 with the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations showing depths of ~ 2 km and ~ 3 km, respectively.
 573 In the 0.25° and 7 km simulations, the circulation depths are $\sim 4 - 5$ km. The depths
 574 of the vorticity anomalies are strongly correlated with the concentration of smoke mix-
 575 ing ratios greater than $\sim 5.0 \times 10^{-9}$ kg/kg (or 5.0 kg/Tg) shown in Fig. 2. This corre-
 576 lation is due to the interplay between smoke, radiative heating anomalies, vertical mo-
 577 tions and vorticity, which is analyzed extensively in Section 4.2.

Figure 8: Vertically averaged, horizontal cross sections of vorticity in s^{-1} contained within the smoke plumes at 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) into the simulations for grid spacings at (a) 2.0° (b) 1.0° (c) 0.25° and (d) 7 km. Vorticity in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-9} kg/kg (or 1.0 kg/Tg) is averaged above 150 hPa to produce these plots.

578 At longer time periods into the simulations, the location and structure of the vortex
 579 is substantially different in each simulation. Figure 10 shows the same kind of plots
 580 as in Fig. 8, only at 41.2 days (0000 UTC 23 September) into the simulations. In the
 581 2.0° run, the maximum in total smoke mixing ratio is very small (not shown) and the
 582 anti-cyclonic vortex has disappeared leaving a region of positive vorticity, which is likely
 583 the result of other synoptic scale features. In the 1.0° case, an anti-cyclonic vortex is still
 584 present at this time, but it is very weak and diffuse with peak values around -1.25×10^{-5}
 585 s^{-1} located over Ireland and the United Kingdom. The 0.25° simulation is still main-
 586 taining a coherent vortex located to the North of Alaska with peak values a bit larger
 587 than $-2.5 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$. The main reason for the differences in location of the plumes is the
 588 height they attain, which results in transport differences from the environmental flows.
 589 The structure of the vortex and the ability to confine the smoke and assist in self-lofting
 590 is part of this process. In the 7 km simulation, the vortex is centered over Vancouver Is-
 591 land with similar peak values of vorticity as the 0.25° case. However, the 7 km run has
 592 much more small-scale variability in the vorticity field with many filaments of positive
 593 vorticity present in the core of the vortex, which could potentially weaken the integrated
 594 circulation through Stokes' theorem.

Figure 9: Zonal mean, vertical cross sections of vorticity in s^{-1} contained within the smoke plumes at 6.2 days (0000 UTC 19 August) into the simulations for grid spacings at (a) 2.0° (b) 1.0° (c) 0.25° and (d) 7 km. Vorticity in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-12} kg/kg is averaged zonally to produce these plots. Black arrows highlight vorticity anomalies contained within high concentrations of smoke (see Fig. 2.)

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4.2 Vortex Lifecycle

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To understand how the anti-cyclonic vortex described above is formed, high frequency output from the 0.25° optimal simulation discussed in Section 3.3 is analyzed. Figure 11 depicts the background relative and absolute vorticity on August 12, 2017 at 1800 UTC in the region where the smoke plume is initialized and 1 h before the smoke injection begins. The plots in Fig. 11 are horizontal cross sections at 150 hPa, which is at or just above the injection height of 12.5 km. The relative vorticity in Fig. 11a shows a broad region of anti-cyclonic vorticity in the smoke plume area denoted on the figure. This region of anti-cyclonic relative vorticity is also present at 100 hPa (not shown), but some bands of cyclonic relative vorticity are present as well. The absolute vorticity in Fig. 11b is positive everywhere, including at higher altitudes, which indicates that the planetary vorticity dominates over the relative vorticity. At these high latitudes, the Coriolis parameter has values over $1 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$, which easily outweighs the relative vorticity in the stratosphere.

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Figure 12 shows the divergence, tilting and material tendency terms from Eq. 4 along with the relative vorticity and divergence all located within the smoke plume at

Figure 10: The same type of plot as in Fig. 8, only at 41.2 days (0000 UTC 23 September) into the simulations following the smoke plume.

611 0000 UTC August 13, which is the end of the 5 h smoke forcing period. These fields are
 612 shown at 150 hPa like those in Fig. 11. The beta term in Eq. 4 is about an order of mag-
 613 nitude smaller than the other terms and can be neglected. The first thing to note is that
 614 the smoke forcing quickly develops an anti-cyclonic relative vorticity anomaly (Fig. 12a)
 615 within the smoke plume with peak values of $\sim -7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is about a factor of
 616 three larger than the background values shown in Fig. 11a. Collocated with this rela-
 617 tive vorticity anomaly is a positive divergence signature (Fig. 12b) indicating the air is
 618 spreading out at this level. The 150 hPa level is near the top of the smoke plume and
 619 there is also an updraft present at this height (not shown), which is consistent with di-
 620 verging air at the top of the rising plume. Given that the absolute vorticity is positive
 621 everywhere (Fig. 11b), the diverging air is inducing a spin-down effect of the cyclonic
 622 absolute vorticity, which results in a negative divergence term (Fig. 12c). The divergence
 623 term values are much larger than those from the tilting term (Fig. 11d) at this time, so
 624 that the material tendency term (Fig. 12e) is almost fully described by the divergence
 625 term. This material tendency term increments the prior relative vorticity approximated
 626 by that shown in Fig. 11a to produce the current relative vorticity (Fig. 12a), which has
 627 a very similar structure to the material tendency and divergence terms.

628 Following the smoke plume in a Lagrangian frame of reference, Fig. 13 shows the
 629 same fields as in Fig. 12 only at 0000 UTC August 14, one day later (1.2 days). The fields

Figure 11: Horizontal cross sections of vorticity in s^{-1} on August 12, 2017 at 1800 UTC (1 h prior to the start of the smoke forcing) in the region where the smoke plume is initialized in the model. Panels (a) and (b) show relative vorticity and absolute vorticity, respectively, both at 150 hPa. The black box denotes the approximate region where the smoke plume is injected into the model. Note the slightly larger colorbar range in panel (b) compared to panel (a), which allows better visibility

630 are also shown at 150 hPa because this is where the peak smoke concentrations are lo-
 631 cated at this time. The smoke plume has grown significantly in size compared to the pre-
 632 vious day and the relative vorticity field (Fig. 13a) shows a large region of anti-cyclonic
 633 vorticity with peak values concentrated in the plume core at or just above $-1 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$.
 634 These values and those from other time periods show that the smoke plume vortex has
 635 a Rossby number ≤ 1 . In the center of the plume, there is a strip of very low vorticity
 636 that separates the core of strong anti-cyclonic vorticity. This region is generally consis-
 637 tent with converging air (negative values of divergence in Fig. 13b), which acts to stretch
 638 the cyclonic absolute vorticity leading to a positive divergence term (Fig. 13c). Outside
 639 of this core region, diverging air (positive values of divergence in Fig. 13b) is leading to
 640 a negative divergence term (Fig. 13c) similar to that described above at 0000 UTC Au-
 641 gust 13 (5 h). The divergence term continues to dominate over the tilting term (Fig. 13d)
 642 with the exception of a region on the western edge of the plume where the shear in the
 643 horizontal and vertical wind is largest. The material tendency term shown in Fig. 13e
 644 reflects the divergence term very closely and the positive values in the center of the plume
 645 are responsible for the strip of very low vorticity observed in Fig. 13a. Smoke is present
 646 at higher altitudes (100 hPa) at this time period and the relative vorticity field at this
 647 level is compact and more uniform with positive divergence everywhere (not shown). This
 648 configuration is very similar to that shown in Fig. 12, which is also located at the top
 649 of the smoke plume.

650 A Lagrangian conceptual model for the formation of smoke plume anti-cyclonic vortices
 651 emerges from these vorticity budget analyses. As the smoke plume absorbs solar radi-
 652 ation and begins to rise, the air diverges at the leading edge of the updraft, which
 653 induces a dilution of the cyclonic absolute vorticity (controlled by the sign of the Cori-
 654 olis parameter). This dilution is a strong spin-down effect of the relative vorticity field,
 655 which dominates over all other terms, producing an anti-cyclonic vortex collocated with
 656 the smoke. The largest concentrations of smoke are present at these upper portions of
 657 the updraft. At levels below the leading edge, a combination of diverging and converg-
 658 ing air associated with variability of the updraft is present that can perturb the struc-
 659 ture of the vortex, but the anti-cyclonic tendency appears to be prominent.

Figure 12: Horizontal cross sections at 150 hPa showing different fields relevant to the budget of relative vorticity within the smoke plume on August 13, 2017 at 0000 UTC (end of the 5 h smoke forcing period). The fields are shown in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-9} kg/kg (or 1.0 kg/Tg). Panels (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e) show relative vorticity (s^{-1}), divergence (s^{-1}), divergence term (s^{-2}), tilting term (s^{-2}) and the material tendency term (s^{-2}), respectively.

660 Continuing to follow the smoke plume, Fig. 14 shows fields relevant to the vorticity
 661 budget at 0000 UTC September 3, which is ~ 21 days after the smoke forcing. At

Figure 13: The same as in Fig. 12 only on August 14, 2017 at 0000 UTC (1.2 days). Panels (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e) show relative vorticity (s^{-1}), divergence (s^{-1}), divergence term (s^{-2}), tilting term (s^{-2}) and the material tendency term (s^{-2}), respectively.

662 this time period, the plume has reached equilibrium and ceased rising, as observed by
 663 the line tracing the center of mass in Fig. 7c. The height of the peak smoke mass is 20
 664 hPa or ~ 26 km, which is the level shown for the fields displayed in Fig. 14. The anti-
 665 cyclonic vortex is still compact and strong at this time period with peak relative vorticity
 666 values of $\sim -1 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ in Fig. 14a. The divergence field (Fig. 14b) is weaker at
 667 this time period as the updraft has diminished and the plume has reached its peak height.

668 Much of the divergence field in the plume is negative with a scattering of some positive
 669 regions, but when averaged over the plume, converging air is found. The dominance of
 670 converging air is more prominent at the top of the plume (10 hPa; not shown), which
 671 is consistent with a decaying updraft transitioning to a downdraft. The divergence term
 672 in Fig. 14c is dominated by positive values, which are driven by the concentration of cy-
 673 clonic absolute vorticity from the converging air. The tilting term is negligible at this
 674 time period so the material tendency term in Fig. 14d is fully described by the diver-
 675 gence effect, which is acting to destroy the anti-cyclonic vortex. This process is basically
 676 the exact opposite to how the anti-cyclonic vortex was formed as outlined above. Even-
 677 tually, the vortex succumbs to this decay mechanism in addition to that from sub-grid
 678 scale dissipation processes as defined by the D term in Eq. 4.

Figure 14: Horizontal cross sections at 20 hPa showing different fields relevant to the budget of relative vorticity within the smoke plume on September 3, 2017 at 0000 UTC (21.2 days). The fields are shown in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-9} kg/kg (or 1.0 kg/Tg). Panels (a), (b), (c) and (d) show relative vorticity (s^{-1}), divergence (s^{-1}), divergence term (s^{-2}), and the material tendency term (s^{-2}), respectively.

679 5 Summary and Conclusions

680 In this paper, the dynamics of wildfire smoke plumes and their dependence on spec-
 681 ified smoke characteristics are examined in global climate simulations at a wide range
 682 of horizontal grid spacings (2.0°, 1.0°, 0.25°, 7 km and 7 km-nonhydrostatic). While the
 683 focus of the study is on the “megafire” event that occurred in British Columbia in Au-
 684 gust of 2017, the results and discussion are relevant to a much wider range of cases. The
 685 main goal of this work is to understand how the resolved energetics of the modeling sys-
 686 tem can affect the plume dynamics and retrieval of important plume properties such as
 687 the total smoke mass and BC fraction, which together determine the BC mass, as well
 688 as the height used to initialize the plume in climate models. Significant uncertainty is
 689 present in estimating these properties, which are determined either by analyzing satel-
 690 lite data (e.g., (Peterson et al., 2018)), which have several impactful assumptions, or by

691 combining climate models with satellite data (e.g., (Yu et al., 2019)). Climate models
 692 are a powerful resource, but they have their own set of uncertainties, such as the treat-
 693 ment of the microphysical and optical properties of smoke particles, initial conditions
 694 and resolution limitations.

695 Many modeling studies are conducted with very coarse grid spacing (e.g., 1°, 2° and
 696 larger) with the smoke plume injected at one or maybe a few model grid points. Sim-
 697 ulations of this type are shown here to be very dissipative, relative to a reference sim-
 698 ulation at 7 km, in terms of horizontal kinetic energy spectra, stratospheric lifetime, peak
 699 plume height and vorticity characteristics. For example, the 2.0° simulation that initial-
 700 izes the smoke plume at one grid point underestimates the stratospheric lifetime by ~
 701 50%, peak plume height by ~ 40% and is missing a large chunk of kinetic energy and
 702 anti-cyclonic vorticity associated with the plume. In the 1.0° simulation that samples the
 703 plume with four grid points, the stratospheric lifetime and peak height are underestimated
 704 by ~ 15% and 23%, respectively, with substantial kinetic energy missing and an anti-
 705 cyclonic vortex that is very weak and diffuse at longer time periods. The 0.25° simula-
 706 tion (64 grid points covering plume) produced only small errors in the lifetime (~ 4%)
 707 and peak height (~ 6%), which is consistent with well-resolved kinetic energy near the
 708 plume scale and a robust vortex. These results indicate that the 0.25° simulation has es-
 709 sentially reached convergence. As a result, in order to produce a dynamically accurate
 710 and well-resolved simulation, the smoke plume must be sampled by the model grid at
 711 ~ 7 - 8 Δx . This “effective resolution” applies to the GEOS model studied here, but other
 712 global modeling systems produce similar results (e.g., (Skamarock et al., 2014)). A 7 km
 713 nonhydrostatic simulation was also conducted and compared to the 7 km hydrostatic ex-
 714 periment to examine the effects of the vertical inertial terms (and sub-grid diffusion) on
 715 the smoke stratospheric lifetime. The nonhydrostatic results show a slightly reduced strato-
 716 spheric lifetime relative to the hydrostatic simulation, indicating that nonhydrostatic dy-
 717 namics produces an overall dissipative effect on the plume vertical transport.

718 Given the above results, sensitivity tests were conducted with 0.25° spacing sim-
 719 ulations to determine the optimal injection height of the plume and BC mass fraction
 720 using the stratospheric lifetime (~ 5 months) and to some extent peak heights (~ 22 km)
 721 (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2019; Das et al., 2021) as the truth
 722 anchor points. These tests indicate that the optimal injection height and BC mass frac-
 723 tion is ~ 12 km and ~ 1%, respectively, assuming an external mixture. If the BC is coated
 724 or internally mixed, as suggested by field data (Lee et al., 2022), an even lower BC mass
 725 fraction will be needed to match the observed lifetime. The ~ 12 km injection height is
 726 supported by satellite observations (Peterson et al., 2018) and previous modeling stud-
 727 ies (Yu et al., 2019). The 1% BC mass fraction is a reduction of 50% from nominal val-
 728 ues and is based on a nearly converged model solution that matches kinetic energy spec-
 729 tra from theory/observations and a 7 km reference simulation. Utilizing the same injec-
 730 tion height, under-resolved simulations at 1.0° or 2.0° grid spacing would require a large
 731 and likely artificial increase in the BC fraction/mass to produce the same stratospheric
 732 lifetime as the well-resolved 0.25° simulation. The lower BC mass fractions identified in
 733 this paper are consistent with recent observations of the BC17 smoke plume described
 734 in Katich and coauthors (2023) after accounting for sampling uncertainty and the larger
 735 area represented in the model.

736 The vorticity dynamics of the smoke plumes is also analyzed to understand the mech-
 737 anisms responsible for the formation and evolution of previously documented anti-cyclonic
 738 vortices (Khaykin et al., 2020; Kablick et al., 2020; Lestrelin et al., 2021), which are shown
 739 here to have peak values of relative, vertical vorticity around $-2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. To provide
 740 this understanding a relative, vertical vorticity budget in a Lagrangian frame of refer-
 741 ence, moving with the smoke plume center of mass, was conducted. The results show that
 742 the formation and evolution of the anti-cyclonic vortex is dominated by the divergence
 743 term with only a small contribution from the tilting term. Further analysis provides the

744 following conceptual model for the formation and destruction of smoke plume anti-cyclonic
 745 vortices. As the plume rises from radiative heating, the air diverges at the top of the up-
 746 draft where the largest concentrations of smoke are found. This divergence aloft induces
 747 a dilution of the background cyclonic absolute vorticity, which is dominated by the Cori-
 748 olis parameter. This dilution is a strong spin-down or negative tendency on the relative
 749 vorticity field, which produces an anti-cyclonic vortex very quickly (5 h) after the ini-
 750 tial injection of smoke. At later times into the simulation (~ 21 days) when the plume
 751 has reached an equilibrium height, the updraft has decayed and the air is largely con-
 752 verging aloft, which induces a concentration of the absolute vorticity field and a posi-
 753 tive relative vorticity tendency that acts to destroy the anti-cyclonic vortex.

754 As described above, there are various sources of uncertainty that cloud the study
 755 of wildfire smoke plumes and their climate effects. The results described in this paper
 756 help to minimize the uncertainty stemming from the resolved energetics of the model-
 757 ing system and illustrates how an under-resolved model configuration can affect the dy-
 758 namics of the smoke plumes and the estimation of important plume properties.

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767 6 Data Availability Statement

768 The GEOS model code is available at <https://github.com/GEOS-ESM/GEOSgcm>.
 769 An overview of the GEOS modeling system, documentation and publications can be found
 770 at https://gmao.gsfc.nasa.gov/GEOS_systems/. The datasets needed to reproduce
 771 the core results of this paper can be found at the following link: [https://doi.org/10](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139799)
 772 [.5281/zenodo.7139799](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139799)

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